

Oral Health Status Among Coal Mine Workers in Madhya Pradesh, India- A Cross-sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to assess the prevalence of periodontal disease among coal miners and provide a basis for planning and evaluating the data from community oral health services in coal mine workers.

The present cross-sectional study was conducted in Coal Mine Field of Umaria District, Madhya Pradesh. The sample size of the study was 500. The information regarding the Medical Problem, oral Hygiene, tobacco use, alcohol use, frequency of sugar intake and visit to the dentist was done with the help of WHO Oral Health Questionnaire for Adults 2013. The clinical examination of the patients had been done according to World Health Organization Oral Health Assessment Form for Adults, 2013.

Majority of participants (75%) were more than 50 years old and having low education status. The high level of tobacco (99.2%) and alcohol (94.6%) consumption was seen among patients. Majority of the participants cleans their teeth once daily (63.8%) with tooth brush and tooth paste. The mean Caries level (DMFT score) was 2.39 ± 2.10 with 57.2% of the workers were having caries. Most of the patients were suffering from periodontal diseases and a large percentage of workers were having shallow and deep pockets.

The coal mine worker is severely affected by the occupational environment. The findings also highlighted the high tobacco and alcohol prevalence, higher periodontal disease and caries prevalence in the population.

KEY WORDS: Alcohol, Coal mine, World Health Organization (WHO), Tobacco

INTRODUCTION:

Good health is a fundamental goal for people and the society. The basic growth of nation is depends upon the productivity and health of its people. According to WHO 'Health is a state of complete, physical mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity'.^[1]

Occupational injuries cause major health problems in all nations.^[2] Coal mining is one of the largest, oldest industries in the world and in India. India is a fifth largest coal reserves and fourth largest coal producer in the world. 81 mining area in eight states are running through coal India.^[3]

Oral health, as already mentioned is an integral part of general health and plays an important role in improving the quality of life. The oral cavity is vulnerable to external agents, and some occupational exposures are associated with oral changes in both hard and soft tissues.^[4]

Environmental hazards contribute to poor oral health in many occupations, as oral cavity is a port of entry for many diseases and present several unique features, which makes it especially prone to occupational diseases.^[5]

The study conducted by Abbas et al. in Telangana district on Underground Coal Mine Workers highlighted the high caries prevalence, higher periodontal disease, traumatic injuries which requires immediate intervention.^[6]

The study by Cengiz et al. on coal mine workers in Turkey found overall prevalence of periodontal disease was found to be 96.2% and was determined by considering subjects with Community

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Periodontal Index scores of 1–4 as diseased and the healthy subjects comprised of a mere 3.8%.^[1]

There is relatively little available literature concerning the oral health status of coal miners. The purpose of this study is to assess the prevalence of periodontal disease among coal miners and provide a basis for planning and evaluating the data from community oral health services in coal mine workers.

Aim:

To Assess the Oral Health Status of Coal Mine Workers of Piparia coal mine at Umaria District, Madhya Pradesh.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Peoples Dental Academy, Bhopal. The present cross-sectional study was done under the Department of Public Health Dentistry, Peoples Dental Academy, Bhopal. The survey was conducted among the coal mine worker in Piparia coal mine at Umaria District, Madhya Pradesh after obtaining Written permission from the Authorities of the coal mine field. It was conducted to find the effect of coal on the oral health of the workers.

The sample size was calculated using the Epiinfo software. The Expected frequency of periodontal disease was 50% and Confidence Interval (C.I.) of 99% was taken. The total sample size calculated was 500. The study included the coal mine workers working at Piparia coal mine in Umaria District except those having systemic disease. The information regarding oral hygiene, tobacco use, alcohol use, frequency of sugar intake and visit to the dentist was done with the help of WHO Oral Health Questionnaire for Adults 2013. The oral Health of the coal mine worker was evaluated by using WHO oral Health assessment Form 2013.

The examination of the subjects was carried out in the selected Coal Mine Field, Subjects were examined seated on the portable dental chair, with the examiner standing approximately in 10 o' clock position, under natural daylight or using artificial illumination. The subjects were positioned so as to receive maximum illumination.

RESULTS:

The present study examined the oral health of 500 coal mine worker. The age of the participant shows that 375 (75%) participants were more than 50 years old and having low education status. The high level of

Table 1: Demographic factors.

Demographic Factors	Categories	Number of Patient	%
Age	25– 35 years	10	2%
	36 – 50 years	115	23%
	>50 years	375	75%
Education	No formal schooling	39	7.8%
	primary school	375	75.0%
	High school	59	11.8%
	Secondary completed	27	5.4%
Tobacco	Graduate or Postgraduate	0	0%
	Yes	484	99.2%
	No	16	0.8%
Alcohol	Yes	573	94.6%
	No	27	5.4%
Sugar Intake	less than one time	64	12.8
	Taken one time	129	25.8
	Taken two times	120	24.0
	Taken 2+ times	187	37.4

tobacco (99.2%) and alcohol (94.6%) consumption were seen among the coal mine workers. The sugar intake was high among coal mine workers. A large number of coal workers used to take sugar more than 2 times a day (37.4%) (Table 1).

Majority of the participants cleans their teeth once daily (63.8%) but still a large percentage of mine (36.2%) workers do not clean their teeth regularly. Most of them use tooth brush with tooth paste for cleaning their teeth (Table 2). Most of the Workers (77.4%) had never visited the dentist and among those who were treated the dentist pain was the main reason for the visit (Table 3).

The Oral health of the workers was poor. The mean caries level (DMFT score) was 2.39 ± 2.10 with 57.2% of the workers were having caries. The Fluorosis was not seen in majority of patients. The major dental problem among them was periodontal health. Most of the patients were suffering from periodontal diseases and a large percentage of workers were having shallow and deep pockets (Table 4).

Table 2: Oral Habits.

		Number of Patient	Percentage
Cleaning of teeth			
Never		12	2.4%
Few times a week		88	17.6%
One times a day		419	63.8%
2 times a day		0	0%
Type			
Toothbrush		457	91.4%
Wooden toothpicks		1	0.2%
Plastic toothpick		0	0%
Thread (dental floss)		0	0%
Charcoal		4	0.8%
Chewstick/miswak		37	7.4%
Finger		1	0.2%
Tooth Paste			
use toothpaste to clean your teeth	Yes	458	91.6%
	No	43	8.6%
Tooth paste contain fluoride	Yes	2	0.4%
	No	0	0%
	Don't know	498	99.6%

Table 3: Oral Health care.

		Number of Patient	Percentage
How long is it since you had visited a dentist?			
Less than 6 months		9	1.8%
6–12 month		5	1.0%
More than 1 year but less than 2 years		14	2.8%
2 years or more but less than 5 year		32	6.4
5 years or more		53	10.6%
Never		387	77.4%
Reason to visit Dentist			
Consultation/advise		0	0%
Pain or trouble with teeth, gums or mouth		98	19.6%
Treatment/ follow-up treatment		8	1.6%
Routine check-up		0	0%
Don't know/don't remember		7	1.4%

Table 4: Dentition Status.

Variables	Levels	Number of patients	%
Caries Experience	No Caries	214	42.8%
	With Caries	286	57.2%
	Normal	428	85.6%
	Questionable	32	6.4%
	Very Mild	17	3.4%
Fluorosis	Mild	9	1.8%
	Moderate	8	1.6%
	Severe	6	1.2%
CPI	Score 0 (Healthy)	27	5.4%
	Score 1 (Bleeding)	65	13.0%
	Score 2 (Calculus)	297	59.4%
	Score 3 (Shallow Pocket)	79	15.8%
	Score 4 (Deep Pocket)	47	9.4%

DISCUSSION:

Standard of living of People has been enhanced by the expansion of industrial activity. Improvement in technology has made jobs very easy in several aspects, but, at the same time, has created new occupational hazards that have drawn public attention^[8] Exposure to chemical, physical and biological agents in the work place can result in adverse effects on workers ranging from simple discomfort and irritation to debilitating occupational diseases.^[8] In addition, the health of industrial workers often goes un cared due to their stressful working conditions, busy schedule and poor economic conditions.^[9]

Although coal mining is one of the oldest industry in the world, India has a long history of commercial coal mining covering nearly 220 years starting from 1774 by M/s Sumner and Healthy of East India Company in the Raniganj Coalfield along the Western bank of river Damodar.^[10] The activities such as drilling, blasting, and transportation are the central cause behind air pollution. The emphasis of large-scale mechanisation of surface mining has resulted in widespread concern about deterioration of environmental quality, especially the increase in concentration of suspended particulate matter (SPM) within and around the mining site. Vehicular traffic on the haul road of mechanised opencast mines has been

identified as the most prolific source of fugitive dust emitted from the surface coal mines.^[11]

Coal dust that once produced contributes to particulate matter in the air which ultimately causes air pollution. Coal dust and residues are one of the major sources of potential harmful elements (PHEs) contamination in air^[12]. The PHEs find their ways to human via dust ingestion, inhalation, and dermal absorption^[13] and oral intake through consumption of contaminated food and water^[14]. The PHEs are considered as hazardous environmental contaminants owing to their toxicity, persistent and bio accumulative nature^[14-15].

In the present study it is noted that the maximum number of mining employees i.e. 50.0% were illiterate or had completed the primary schooling (32.4%). Similar high percentage illiteracy was noted in the coal mining workers of Telangana^[6]. The studies conducted on other types of mine worker also had similar result like 62.4% workers were illiterate in stone plants in Rajasthan.^[16]

Similar level of literacy was seen in the Brazillian metal plant workers,^[17] cement mining workers in Sirohi district of Rajasthan.^[18] Contrastingly, around 67.7% of the sea farer had the secondary level education.^[19]

ORAL HABITS:

Usage of the tobacco products in the present mining employees (99.2%) was high in comparison to the general population (61.67%) and similar levels were found in coal mine workers (84%) in Telangana^[11], battery mining workers of Kanpur city (85.71%) (20). Contrastingly, less consumption (58%) of the tobacco products was seen in the Jordanian battery industries workers^[21]. Alcohol was consumed by 80.80% of the mining workers, which is way higher in comparison to the general population (60.42%). However in the study by Cengiz et al.^[7], it is seen that the working population consumed less alcohol then the control group or the general population. In disagreement to this finding less consumption (2.3%) of the Alcohol was reported in the coal mining workers of Telangana.^[6]

According to the earlier literature, physically tedious work drives people to consume alcohol and tobacco which further deteriorate their oral health.^[22] Another reason which can quoted for the high prevalence of adverse Oral habit practice in the coal workers is the peer influence, as most of the task which they have to perform in the team^[6], they might acquire these habits as influenced by peers.

ORAL HYGIENE HABITS

The finding of the present study shows 91.4% of the workers use tooth brush to clean their teeth which was in contradiction to the study conducted by Cengiz et al.^[7] where only 25% coal mine worker use tooth brush to clean their teeth.

The result of the study were in accordance to the study by Abbas et al,^[6] on Telangana coal mine workers where 100% workers used to brush their tooth once daily. Similar high percentage of brushing once in a day in brass mining workers was reported by Tirthet al.,^[23] and construction workers (76.9%) of Chennai city by Sakthi et al.^[24]

SUGAR INTAKE:

The sugar intake was high among coal mine workers. A large number of coal workers used to take sugar more than 2 times a day (37.4%) and 24.0% of workers used to take sugar two times a day. The result was in consistent with the result of the study done by Dabhadker et al. on nutritional status of coal mine workers in Chhatishgarh where they also found high intake of sugar among coal mine workers.^[25]

According to Dabhadker et al.^[25] mining is energy demanding process, creates psychophysiological stress on the body and also increases the rate of basal metabolism thus enhances the body's energy requirements and thus increases the sugar consumption by coal mine workers.

DENTAL VISIT:

The majority of coal mine workers (77.4%) had never visited to the dentist. Among the workers (23.6%) who had visited the dentist pain is the main (19.6%) reason for visit. The study shows low percentage of visiting dentist in comparison to the study of Cengiz et al. on Turkey coal mine workers population where 37.7% of the individuals had visited the dentist.^[7]

DENTAL CARIES:

The prevalence of dental caries in the present study was 57.2%, with a mean DMFT index of 2.39 ± 2.10 which was similar to the findings of the study conducted by Abbas et al.,^[6] with mean DMFT level 2.32 ± 2.99 . Prevalence of dental caries in present study is in accordance with AE Van Der Merwe et al., where 55.43% of 92 subjects showed dental caries.^[26] In another study by Duraiswamy et al.,^[27] prevalence of dental caries was 73.7% with the mean DMFT index found to be 3.13, as compared to 2.39 in the present study.

About more than half of study subjects showed caries in the present study which can be attributed to their oral hygiene practices, absence of dental care in the locality, fear of dental treatment, lack of utilization of appropriate care provided by mine authorities, negligence and most of all lack of awareness about oral health.

PERIODONTAL DISEASE:

Periodontal disease is the most prevalent condition seen in the study population with 95.8% subjects having unhealthy periodontium in terms of gingival bleeding and/or periodontal pockets. These findings are in accordance with those of Solanki et al., and Rushabh J Dagli et al., where 95.1% of subjects are periodontally diseased with only 4.9% free of disease and 98.25% periodontal disease prevalence with only 1.75% of subjects having healthy periodontium respectively.^[16,28] The present findings also coincide with those of Santhosh Kumar et al., where the prevalence of periodontal disease of any degree was found to be 98.2%, that is, only 1.8% of the green marble mine workers were free of periodontal disease.^[29] Present study findings are in contrast to those of AE Van Der Merwe et al., where 40.2% periodontal disease prevalence was observed.^[26]

A very bad oral hygiene of the workers would be the foremost factor associated with gingivitis and periodontitis of the workers. Age could be another factor for such an unhealthy periodontium because the mean age of study population is around 50 years. Also, the general health condition was not assessed in the present study. This was a limitation of this study as this could have influenced their periodontal status. Workers always were exposed to coal dust and silica particles which might be associated with tooth wear, gingivitis and periodontitis.

Continued usage of tobacco in either smoking form or chewing form might as well influence periodontal status of the workers. Their rotating shift work schedules could influence their body physiology and metabolism which in turn could have an indirect periodontal influence. Improper tooth brushing techniques, neem stick usage for cleaning teeth also could have an impact on gingival recession, loss of attachment.

CONCLUSION:

The coal mine worker is severely affected by the Occupational Environment. Coal mine workers had poor oral health status. The findings also

highlighted the high tobacco and alcohol prevalence, higher periodontal disease and caries prevalence in the population.

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